

TECHNOLOGY OF GROWING, HARVESTING AND STORAGE OF LEMON PLANTS.

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the morphological characteristics of the lemon plant, cultivation technology, medicinal properties of its fruit, methods of propagation of lemon seedlings and preservation of its fruit are shown.

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS:

Lemon [Citrus Limon (L.) Burm] is a tree up to 4 m tall, belonging to the rutabaga family. The leaves of the plant are thick, oval-shaped, sharp-pointed, dark green, shiny. They are located in a row on the stems with a short band. The flowers of the plant are small, have a pleasant smell, and are white in color.

it turns yellow when ripe. The taste is sour, fruit with many seeds. Now mainly subtropical Europe, North America and Asia grown in countries.

The soft, runny and very sour pulp of the fruit is mainly water and citric acid, as well as in its composition contains sugar, ascorbic acid, A, V, C, R drugs. Fruit-pectin substances, potassium salts, copper and other micro-elements are available. The bark contains 0.6% essential oil.

In later times, lemon Central Asian republics, especially Cultivation on a large scale in greenhouses in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan is resurrected and a good harvest is being made.

PAYMENT METHODS:

Propagation from grafting. Grafting is a process in the plant body the period when the bat is actively moving is carried out in spring or summer, at other times of the year it is less effective. It is mostly 1-2 years old saplings are used, but on the branches of older trees can be welded. For the graft, there should be a lemon seedling it is not necessary, other citrus fruits also handle it very well. Lemon is bitter If grafted to an orange tree, especially a small tree should be grown when there is, good results are achieved. The most widely used method of welding is pen and bud

is welding.

Welding from a pen. This method is so simple that even amateurs can be scolded.

The hard part is finding suitable healthy, abundantly yielding domestic lemons. A branch with a short leaf (about 10 cm) is taken for the pen. It can be wrapped in a wet cloth or polythene until it starts working. It should be stored in a cool place. There are several methods of welding from a pen:

Method 1. Break and connect. This is the simplest method used when the thickness of the weld and the weld is equal. The weld may be a bit thick. The weld is cut with a sharp knife at a height of 7-10 cm from the ground and a 2-3 cm deep crack is made in the middle.

A graft with 3-5 buds is inserted into the resulting slit. Both sides are sharpened by 2-3 cm in length so that the welder can enter the weld. It is important to pay attention to the fact that their shells touch each other from one side. If the weld is thick, it is possible to connect two pins, they may be of different types. The joint is wrapped with polyethylene, plasticine is glued over it.

Another method of welding is bark, butt welding. The weld should be a bit larger than the welder. The weld is cut at a height of 6-8 cm from the ground, and a small (2-3 cm) slot is opened from the shell on the side, and a rod is inserted into it. Usually, the bevel cut of the stem corresponds to the bark cut.

Several branches can be connected to one base. In this case, the slot is opened as needed. In order for the welded pen to hold well, a wet cloth is wrapped below the joint and a plastic bottle with a cut neck is placed over it. Or you can put on a simple

polythene bag and tie it under the weld. As a result, the air around the pen becomes more humid and allows it to trap.

Citrus seedlings are transplanted in the second half of March in the southern regions of Uzbekistan, and in the first half of April in the northern regions. Seedlings can be transplanted in early autumn - until September 15.

To transfer lemon seedlings, the soil of the greenhouse should be leveled well and worked to a depth of 50-60 cm. 60-80 tons of rotted manure, 600 kg of superphosphate and 150 kg of potash fertilizers are applied per hectare. It is necessary that the seedlings of citrus plants are healthy and well developed. 10-12 days before transplanting, the soil of the greenhouse is watered drip by drop until it is full of moisture. After planting areas are planned, the pits are dug to a depth of 60 cm.

During planting, 10-15 kg of rotted manure, 100-150 g of superphosphate and 50 g of potassium fertilizers are added to each pit.

One- and two-year-old lemon seedlings with well-developed roots should have up to 3-4 first-order branches with a trunk thickness of 0.7-0.8 cm, and two-year-old lemon seedlings should have at least 1 cm of second-order branches and a trunk thickness.

In autumn, lemon seedlings must be planted together with the soil adjacent to the roots, because otherwise some of the seedlings may dry out. Transplanting, as well as excess branches that thicken the branches, as well as damaged roots are cut off. Seedlings are planted using planting boards for transfer on stakes stuck in pits. In this case, the root neck of the seedlings must be 2-3 cm above the soil surface.

After the seedling is planted, the soil is compacted by pouring a bucket of water into each hole. Then, leaving 25-30 cm from both sides of each row, it is watered drip by drop. In the first year, seedlings can be moved to a row with an interval of 1 m from each other, after a year, all the excess seedlings should be dug up and transferred to a permanent place in new greenhouses from March 15 to April 15.

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When transplanted before the citrus plants are 3 years old

holds up well. When larger plants are transplanted

the roots are damaged, the leaves are partially shed, the growth is behind remains, and such plants come into harvest later.

Plants to be transplanted are dug up with soil. Seedlings are watered 3-4 days before digging so that the soil around the roots does not spread. As the soil of the greenhouse is prepared, pits for planting seedlings are dug. The first row of pits is dug 1 m away from the northern wall of the greenhouse, leaving a 2 m gap between the rows. Seedlings are placed in the pit with a special board or shovel. The space between

the soil around the roots of the seedlings and the wall of the pit is filled with a nutrient mixture, and this mixture is filled with a blunt-pointed stake. After burying the pit, the seedling is watered through a bucket until it becomes soft. Then, the soil around the seedlings is leveled and softened, and watering holes are opened on both sides of the row. A distance of 30 cm is left between the seedlings and the watering can. After the seedlings are transplanted, they are watered once more so that they take root well.

Ripe fruits are cut with a special fruit picker or garden shears. The fruit is gradually caught by hand from the bottom, and its band is cut from the side of the calyx.

Lemons are picked not later than when the skin starts to turn yellow or when the diameter of the fruits is 5-6 cm. These fruits should be picked on dry days. Fruits picked on hot days are quickly poisoned and rot.

When picking ripe fruits, their quality improves and their size increases. Fruit boxes should not be shaken violently when transported by hand, cart or car. It is necessary to pick damaged, contaminated and infected fruits in separate boxes.

The fruits delivered to the warehouse are stored in boxes until sorting and consumption.

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